

DISTINCTIVE FEATURES OF IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY FOR TEACHING CHILDREN OF A PREPARATORY GROUP ON THE BASIS OF MULTIMEDIA TOOLS TO COMPOSE A CREATIVE STORY

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Abstract. *This article provides scientific information about the peculiarities of teaching children of a preparatory group on the basis of multimedia to compose a creative story.*

Keywords: *interest, ability, computer, creativity, collective, multimedia, technology, speech, creative, idea.*

Taking into account the interest, ability, worldview and age of the upbringing, taking into account the fact that his eyes are tired, developing the knowledge of the upbringing, improving his memory, concentrating, developing his abilities through a computer tool are also psychological features of passing training through multimedia technologies. As our autonomous president said, " Our main goal is to achieve the opportunity of young people to receive quality education, to create all the necessary conditions for the realization of their abilities and talents. "The goal of maturing a person of independent thinking, creativity and high spirituality is, of course, embodied in our country, when the emphasis is placed on the physical and spiritual maturity of the younger generation as a priority of state policy. President Of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. M. Mirziyoyev put forward 5 important initiatives, the tasks set out on the basis of a new system of work in the social, spiritual and educational spheres dictate the implementation of important measures related to youth education. Also, the decree of June 17, 2018 on the state program "Youth – our future" shows that the complex tasks aimed at youth education have become more relevant in the life of society and the nation.

The requirements noted in these documents depend on the content and essence of the innovative changes made in the system of continuing education, and mainly apply to the preschool education process. Because at this stage, the upbringing is armed with the basics of literacy, elements of computational thinking, labor skills and personality spirituality. Therefore, the modern educational system, its goals and objectives the educational process that serves the development of our country should correspond to the solution of the problem posed before it. These are subjects in the modern educational system, in particular, it is necessary to regularly raise the creative activities of preschool teachers in accordance with the level of development of society.

R. X. Djuraev believes that in the development of the qualities of creativity in children, the principles of humanity, continuity, continuity, tolerance, independence and self-confidence, a person-oriented approach, awareness, activity and advanced development of education are characteristic.

G. Amirova notes that the manifestation of creativity in pictorial-artistic activity is the development of the child's motivation. These are: in the organization of daily observation of the phenomena of the environment; communication with art; provision of material; taking into account

the individual individuality of the child; Organization of the creative environment in visual activity; consists of such as the justification of the assignment.

During the implementation of a certain activity in the development of creative abilities, M. Toirova recognizes the influence of the ability to freely choose the sequence of actions, the developing environment, the warm, friendly environment in the family and community. “It is important to constantly inspire the child to creativity, to be resistant to failure, to patiently accept even any ideas that cannot be realized in life. Not to allow reproach and condemnation” It is also effective to organize training processes on a multimedia basis when attracting children's attention. We know that the transience of training through multimedia it allows those brought up to both see and listen and do it together at the same time to master the knowledge onslaught and enjoy it.

Academic S. Gulomov and several scientists say as proof of our opinion that: “The storage of information in memory increases by 25-30% if students receive the materials being given on a visual (video) basis. In addition to this, the preservation of materials in memory increases by 75% if educational materials are given in the form of audio, video, and graphics.” In Multimedia technology, training processes are carried out through a number of principles. Examples include consistency, sequence, and age-appropriate principles. The principle of intelligibility through Multimedia technology is the process of displaying information stored on a computer and needed for training through a monitor. Educators should pay all their attention and attention to the fact that in the process of training learners will be able to understand new knowledge. The new materials being taught should not cause difficulties for the child, be understandable in accordance with their age.

Through Multimedia, it is possible to develop the psychological characteristics of those brought up, change their worldview and form their abilities. Nowadays, books, newspapers and pamphlets have become the main means of information. Using them, children's broad thinking and thinking developed. And through the use of Multimedia in training, the worldview and thinking of children also develop through the development of knowledge in both text and animation. One of the peculiarities of organizing activities through a computer is the influence of this computer on the growth of children. With this in mind, it is permissible for those trained in the training process not to use computers and mobile devices for more than 15 minutes. Otherwise, negative consequences begin to surface in the child.

After the establishment of the Federal state educational standard, the structure of schools and preschool education organization changed at a great speed towards good. Preparation for the effective organization of classes through modern multimedia programs to eliminate the shortcomings and problems that are prominent in society should be organized in all educational institutions, except preschool educational organizations. Here are such processes that the knowledge occupied by children should not be limited to mastering the concepts of keyboard and screen of course. The organization of education through modern computer tools helps not only to improve the effectiveness of the course process, but also to develop and improve the professional qualifications of pedagogical educators. As part of the professional skills, the culture of the educator's use of multimedia programs through modern computer tools also occupies a large place.

The activities of the modern preschool organization using the multimedia program are one of the formative education and methods of working on oneself, aimed at improving the abilities of children (collecting and processing information, conducting experiments, analyzing the results obtained). There are various forms and means of refining the knowledge acquired by educators

through modern computer technologies, which can be used in practice gradually. We can cite below examples from several forms and methods aimed at shaping competence when working with educators through modern computer technologies:

Workshop - modern creative lessons of the computer-developed workshop focused on the development of creative thinking and the creation of innovative projects.

Modeling of games. Business and skillfully developed educational games through Game programs involve modeling the real process, during which correct professional decisions are made based on the analysis of situations related to the lesson created on the basis of multimedia. Solving collective problems, group discussion or mental attack; trainings in large and preparatory groups to improve knowledge acquired through a computer tool; development of a sense of self-confidence; scientific and practical conferences based on the results of innovative activities of a preschool educational organization.

Pedagogical environment - educates educators in the search for the latest research in the field of psychology and pedagogy, methodological literature, helps to find different ways to solve pedagogical issues, develops the skills of logical thinking and obtaining evidence of their own thoughts.

This tool provides methods for assessing user responses as well as the actions they perform:

1. comprehensive knowledge;
2. pedagogical knowledge, abilities, skills;
3. the ability to find solutions to difficult problems, agility.

Master class. Its main task is to get acquainted with pedagogical experience, effective methods and methods, the work system, scientific articles and all educational tools applied to the pedagogue to achieve effective results.

General important competencies of the educator in the preschool educational organization (6-7 years old) Communicative competence is the skill of being able to apply in different situations from types of conversation. Game competence-the creative benefit of a child from experience, knowledge and skills in the process of play and its implementation. Is the basis for the educational environment. Social competence is the skill of self-control in conversations with adults and peers in life situations, following educational rules and norms.,

Information technology is a broad class of disciplines and fields of activity related to data management and processing technologies, as well as data creation, including the use of computer technology. In recent years, Information Technology has often been understood as computer technology. In particular, information technology deals with the use of computers and software to store, modify, protect, process, transmit and receive information.

Conclusions and recommendations. So, the use of multimedia presentations makes it possible to make classes emotionally colorful, attractive, to arouse great interest in the child. They help the lesson to pass well efficiently through excellent visual weapons and visual material. So, in training, the use of multimedia presentations on the cultivation of speech, teaching literacy, mathematics, music, acquaintance with the outside world children ensures that children are active in checking the signs and characteristics of the object and visually emphasizing it.

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